

**Meise
Botanic Garden**

Science Collections Strategy

**Meise Botanic Garden,
2026 - 2035**

Contents

Executive summary	3
1. Vision for our scientific collections	4
Our vision for the science collections	5
2. A brief history of Meise Botanic Garden and its collections	6
3. Current status of the collections and their importance in modern plant science	9
Living plant collection	11
Seed bank	11
Herbarium	12
Molecular collection	13
Library, archives, and art collection	13
4. International partnerships and collaborations	14
5. Science collections ambitions	16
Ambition 1 - Strengthening the impact of our collectons for research, conservation, and policymaking	18
Safeguarding the Belgian flora and contributing to global conservation challenges	19
Taking on global change challenges for plant diversity	19
Contributing to food and health security through conserving crop genetic resources	19
Understanding and recording biodiversity	20
Ambition 2 - Securing the collections for future generations	28
Building a state-of-the-art infrastructure	28
Integrating international best practices in collection management	29
Securing long-term preservation of collection data	29
Ensuring the continuation of collection expertise and knowledge	30
Ambition 3 - Expanding global access to our collections and their data	32
Expand digital access	32
Improve physical access	35
Ambition 4 - Engaging the public with biodiversity through collections	36
Ambitie 5 - Strengthening our position as a global centre of excellence in collections and data	39
A key partner in the DiSSCo infrastructure	39
Advancing Central African collections and capacity building	40
Acronyms	42
Colophon	44

Executive summary

Meise Botanic Garden's *Science Collections Strategy 2026–2035* outlines a plan for maintaining and enhancing the Garden's science collections to support scientific research, conservation, and public engagement over the next decade.

With over 225 years of history, the Garden manages a diverse collection including living plants, seeds, herbarium specimens, molecular samples, library resources and archives. These collections are essential for understanding biodiversity, addressing challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and food security, and fulfilling international commitments, including the Global Biodiversity Framework and the EU Biodiversity strategy for 2030.

Over the past decade, we have made significant progress in digitising our collections, with three million herbarium specimens accessible online via platforms like the Global Biodiversity Information Facility. Building further on these achievements, the strategy focuses on improving access, preservation, and the scientific relevance of our collections.

The strategy also reaffirms our long-standing Central African partnerships, supporting the restoration and digitisation of key collections and strengthening regional capacity for biodiversity research.

The strategy is guided by five key ambitions:

- 1. Strengthening the impact of our collections for research, conservation, and policymaking:** Prioritising taxa and regions of expertise, adopting technologies such as DNA sequencing and artificial intelligence, and ensure collections meet research and conservation needs.
- 2. Securing the collections for future generations:** Upgrading collection facilities, enhancing preservation standards, and implementing a unified collection management system.
- 3. Expanding global access to our collections and their data:** Increasing digitisation efforts, improving online accessibility, and developing tools to enhance data curation and interoperability.
- 4. Engaging the public with biodiversity through collections:** Developing new exhibitions and interactive platforms to connect broader audiences with the collections, fostering public understanding of biodiversity.
- 5. Strengthening our position as a global centre of excellence in collections and data:** Strengthening expertise in biodiversity informatics, sustainable collection management, and international collaboration.

1.

**Vision for our
scientific collections**

Meise Botanic Garden houses an extensive and diverse array of collections, reflecting a rich history spanning more than 225 years. Today, these collections encompass over four million specimens and accessions, including living plants, seeds, herbarium specimens, molecular samples, library holdings, archives, and botanical art. These unique collections, curated by our specialised staff dedicated to their technical and scientific management, form a critical resource for research in the plant sciences. They are essential for fundamental research, including taxonomy and evolution, and the conservation of plant diversity. They also support applied research, such as studies on crop wild relatives, help raise public awareness about urgent concerns such as the biodiversity crisis and social issues, and are used to address policy-related needs by providing a comprehensive understanding of biodiversity changes in response to global change. While this document focuses mainly on preserved collections, the *Living Collections Strategy* covers the living collections and seed bank in detail.

Our collections are widely used by researchers globally. Advances in digitisation and international collaborations have greatly improved access to collections and literature, transforming the way scientific knowledge is managed and utilised. Three decades ago, collections were still predominantly managed physically and scientific knowledge was mainly organised on paper, making their retrieval often time-consuming. Today, scientists benefit from the digital revolution, making it easier to explore and interact with collections and literature. Meise Botanic Garden has been at the forefront of this transformation, leading efforts to digitise its botanical collections and library. Major achievements include digitising approximately three million herbarium specimens, now openly accessible via our collection portal (botanicalcollections.be) and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF). The Garden also plays a key role in the Distributed System of Scientific Collections (DiSSCo), a European Research Infrastructure, which will enhance access to natural science collections further. The Garden leads the DiSSCo Flanders consortium, unlocking diverse collections across Belgium.

The *Science Collections Strategy* works in conjunction with the *Science Strategy*, *Living Collections Strategy*, and *Public Outreach Strategy* to achieve the overarching mission of Meise Botanic Garden: “Building a sustainable future through discovery, research, and conservation of plants”. It ensures our collections support international commitments such as the Global Strategy for Plant Conservation (GSPC), the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework under the Convention on Biological Diversity, and the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, a central component of the European Green Deal.

Our vision for the science collections

In a rapidly changing world, our vision focuses on developing, preserving, and sharing collections to address critical challenges, such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and shifting societal needs. We will further develop and preserve our collections while adhering to the highest professional, legal, and ethical standards. Through global collaboration, we will ensure our collections remain relevant and continue to support core activities in research, conservation, and public engagement. To uphold our leadership in collection management and digitisation, we will continue providing essential services to the global scientific community, supporting innovative, collaborative research to tackle global challenges.

A brief history of Meise Botanic Garden and its collections

Understanding the Garden's historical collection development is the basis for a modern collection strategy. Key events, influenced by researchers' interests, strategic choices, and sociopolitical factors, reveal the dynamic relationship between collections and research. Collections inspire research, which in turn enhances collections with new specimens, data, and identifications. Emerging research priorities continue to drive the growth and evolution of the collections.

The origins of Meise Botanic Garden date back to 1797 when Brussels established its first botanic garden, initially connected to the *École centrale du département de la Dyle*, where the systematically classified plant collection supported science classes.

Urban renewal projects in the 1820s threatened the survival of the garden. To save the living collections, in 1826, a group of botanists and horticulturists founded with the support of the city authorities and King Wilhelm, the company *Koninklijke maatschappij van kruid-, bloem- en boomkwekerijen der Nederlanden*, and established the *Kruidtuin van Brussel (Jardin Botanique de Bruxelles)* on the northern outskirts of the city, with its official opening in 1829. The company's intent was mainly economic. This was the era of explorers and plant hunters who travelled to overseas territories, often colonies, in search of new and valuable plant species. These discoveries were in high demand, as European plant growers and collectors paid substantial sums for exotic novelties. King Wilhelm approved the establishment of a Royal Herbarium, but as Belgium neared independence, director Carl Ludwig Blume moved to Leiden (South Holland) and transferred the valuable Asian herbarium there, which left the young Belgian state without a national herbarium.

In 1830, the botanic garden became a battleground during the Belgian Revolution, causing damage to the collections and equipment. This placed a heavy financial burden on the company, and in response, it sold part of its land, rebranded itself as the *Société royale d'horticulture de Belgique*, and shifted focus to the commercial trade of vegetables, fruits, and ornamental plants. In 1854, the garden sought to strengthen its scientific mission by appointing botanist Henri-Guillaume Galeotti as director, under whom the living collection expanded and a botanical museum was established. However, urgent renovations and a costly heating system were financially unsustainable and led to the society's dissolution in 1870.

The establishment of the *Rijksplantentuin (Jardin botanique de l'État)* in 1870, supported by Barthélémy Dumortier, revived the Garden's scientific mission. This was accompanied by renewed efforts to build an herbarium. Major acquisitions followed, including Galeotti's Mexican collection, Carl von Martius' herbarium, and François Crépin's extensive collection. By 1885, the herbarium had grown to 400,000 specimens of phanerogams and cryptogams, solidifying its status as one of Europe's major herbaria, and as a centre for Central and South American botany. These collections supported critical works such as *Flora Brasiliensis* and *Crépin's Flore de Belgique*.

The library originated from the collection of the Royal Horticultural Society of Belgium. It was significantly enriched by two major acquisitions: the library of Barthélémy Dumortier, purchased after his death in 1878,

and the collection of François Crépin, donated during his tenure as director from 1877 to 1901. Over the years, the library has grown further through acquisitions and exchanges facilitated by two periodicals: one published by the Garden and the other by the Royal Botanical Society of Belgium. The living collection also expanded, new glasshouses were built, and ornamental plants were cultivated to supply governmental and public buildings.

The Forestry Museum at the Botanical Garden of Brussels.

The creation of Congo Free State by King Leopold II in the late 19th century and later colonisation by the Belgian state, brought a focus on the Central African flora. Extensive collections of plants and fungi from Central Africa were added (later, the herbaria from the Royal Museum of Central Africa and Institut Agricole de Gembloux were also transferred to the Garden), facilitating landmark publications such as *Flore d'Afrique centrale* and *Flore illustrée des champignons d'Afrique centrale*. The Garden served as a centre for botanical and horticultural collaboration by hosting the Royal Botanical Society of Belgium, the Belgian Society for Microscopy, and some local horticultural societies. Simultaneously, the Garden's public role expanded through adding sculptures and terraces designed in various architectural styles, as well as the creation of a Forestry Museum, transforming the Garden into a space for both scientific study and public enjoyment.

In the 20th century, as the Garden faced space constraints in Brussels, plans were made to relocate to the Bouchout domain in Meise. In 1938, the Belgian State agreed to buy the domain of Bouchout in Meise from the Royal Family. From 1939 onward, parts of the collections were gradually transferred from Brussels to Meise.

The move to Meise marked the start of significant investments, including several glasshouses and the publicly accessible 'Plant Palace'. A dedicated herbarium and library building was constructed (1959–1962), and expanded in the 1980s to accommodate the growing collections. The Garden's herbarium continued to flourish with acquisitions of multiple private and institutional collections. Improved travel conditions for amateur and professional botanists increased collecting in south-west Europe. The living plant collection was substantially expanded, partly due to increasing international collaborations and exchanges between botanical gardens, and a seed bank was established. In 1967, the institution was assigned a new official name: National Botanical Garden of Belgium. That same year, the domain became a protected landscape.

In recent decades, Meise Botanic Garden has continued to enhance its expertise in plant and fungal diversity across Belgium, Europe, and Central Africa, while expand-

ing to areas such as the sub-Antarctic and Indian Ocean islands, Southeast Asia, and the marine Indo-Pacific. Key taxonomic groups in flowering plants include Rubiaceae (coffee family), Balsaminaceae (balsam family), and Fabaceae (legume family), as well as fungi, lichens, diatoms, macroalgae, and myxomycetes. A significant addition in 2006 was Henri Van Heurck's (1838 – 1909) collection, including diatoms (among the world's ten largest collections), vascular plants, mosses, wood, economic botany specimens, books and botanical models.

In 2014, administrative responsibility for the Garden was transferred from the federal to the Flemish authority. Although a substantial part of its scientific collections remains federal property, they are entrusted to the Garden on a permanent loan. Ongoing modernisation efforts according to the Garden's master plan, including now completed renovations of the Plant Palace, the construction of a new glasshouse complex and seed bank, the development of several new thematic gardens, and the upcoming renovation of the collection and research building, will ensure its role as a global centre for botanical research, conservation, and education well into the future.

The Library at the Botanical Garden of Brussels.

Current status of the collections and their importance in modern plant science

The diverse collections of Meise Botanic Garden underpin studies of biodiversity across a broad range of taxonomic groups, including plants, fungi, algae, and protists, and across ecosystems ranging from the rainforests of Central Africa to aquatic habitats in Antarctica. Researchers from the Garden, as well as external users, use these resources to describe species diversity, assess climate change impacts, and explore the evolutionary relationships of plants, fungi and algae. This work informs conservation priorities and biodiversity related policy. The living collection and seed bank play a vital role in preserving genetic diversity and supporting species recovery efforts.

Herbaria and libraries have always been, and continue to be, essential to plant taxonomy. Herbaria house voucher specimens, including type specimens (the refer-

ence specimens from which species are first described), ensuring accuracy and consistency in taxonomic research. They are also crucial for species discovery, with many undescribed species still hidden within these collections. Libraries are central in preserving and disseminating taxonomic knowledge. The value of these collections now extends far beyond taxonomy, offering rich data resources enhanced by technological advances. Herbaria provide not only plant specimens but also critical spatiotemporal information captured in specimen labels. These data are invaluable for understanding global biodiversity patterns and the origins of plant diversity. Emerging technologies have expanded the ways in which specimens are used. For example, genomic data can now be extracted from specimens, supporting evolutionary research and resolving long-standing taxonomic challenges.

Each specimen has its own story to tell. The label reveals when, where, and by whom it was collected, while the specimen itself offers valuable trait data, such as morphological, biochemical, and genetic information. With millions of specimens in Meise Botanic Garden's herbarium, alongside countless natural science collections worldwide, these specimens serve as a vital reference for documenting Earth's natural history.

The global geographical scope of the herbarium (<https://doi.org/10.15468/wrthhx>) with hotspots for Central Africa and our native flora. The map displays only the georeferenced specimens (ca. 24%). Significant effort is required to georeference the remaining specimens in our collection.

Herbarium

The herbarium is ranked as the 15th largest in the world. It contains over four million specimens representing more than 220,000 species, including over 64,000 type specimens. The collection encompasses a broad array of taxonomic groups including flowering plants, ferns, mosses, macroalgae, diatoms, fungi, lichens, and myxomycetes. Specialised subcollections, such as the Economic Botany Collection and a comprehensive wood collection, further enhance its value. Geographically, the herbarium has a global scope, with notable strengths for Central Africa, Belgium, South-western Europe, the Indo-Pacific, and Arctic regions, as well as historically significant collections from Latin America and other parts of the world. Most specimens are preserved as pressed and dried plants mounted on herbarium sheets or dried fungi stored in cardboard boxes, but the collection also includes microscope slides (such as pollen, histological preparations, and diatoms), plants, fungi, and algae preserved in alcohol, and samples of fruits and seeds.

While our herbarium is particularly rich in specimens from the 19th and 20th centuries, current research, curation, and digitisation efforts keep the collection a dynamic centre for research. Scientists both locally and globally visit, study, and add to the collections, increasing scientific collaboration and knowledge. Expanding by approximately 15,000 specimens annually, it continues to grow in scope and significance. The collection is increasingly accessible online, with high-resolution digital images and label data available for 2.5 million specimens to date, and this number is continuously growing. We also see a marked increase in the access and use of our digital collections, with overall more than one million views on botanicalcollections.be, GBIF, and JSTOR Global Plants, and currently 1,651 data citations on GBIF. The herbarium attracts over 50 scientific visitors annually (accounting for more than 300 visitor days) and lends out more than 1,000 specimens each year, supporting research in plant sciences worldwide.

Molecular collection

The molecular collection, a relatively recent addition, supports DNA-based taxonomy, phylogenetics, population genetics, and molecular identification services. It comprises tissue samples that are frozen or preserved in silica gel and DNA extracts. The collection is rapidly expanding and has become an indispensable resource for researchers across various disciplines. Currently, the collection houses over 10,000 tissue samples, and around 20,000 DNA extracts in -20°C and -80°C freezers. Integration of the molecular collection into the Garden's Collection Management System (CMS) is still pending, as well as integrating it in global networks such as the Global Genome Biodiversity Network (GGBN), aiming to make the collection accessible to external researchers. Efforts are also underway to expand the collection further by gathering molecular samples from living accessions to document their genetic diversity.

Library, archives, and art collection

The library, archives, and art collection form a comprehensive resource for botanical and historical research, complemented by access to electronic literature.

The **library**, one of Europe's leading botanical libraries, houses about 250,000 volumes, including books, journals, offprints, and historical maps. Its focus includes plant systematics, floristics, ecology, ethnobotany, horticulture, and the history of botany and related fields, with special emphasis on the flora of Belgium and Central Africa. The library also preserves a rare collection of 3,500 historical works, mostly illustrated, dating back to the 15th century, including treasures such as *Opus Ruralium Commodorum* (1486) and the works of Rembert Dodoens (1517 – 1585). Other highlights include rare printed herbaria, and an extensive nature print collection. Through membership of the Biodiversity Heritage Library, our digitised books are available in BHL.

The **archives**, dating back to the foundation of the Garden, preserve a wealth of valuable materials, including documents, letters, and field notes. These resources provide insights into the history of scientific practices and theories, as well as vegetation records and phenological data. They offer invaluable documentation of specimens,

including detailed morphological observations, measurements, ecological data, and more. They also chronicle the extensive historic networks of botanists and the wide-reaching exchange of botanical collections. The archives serve as a rich resource for researchers across various disciplines, including natural sciences, humanities, and arts.

The **art and heritage collection** includes thousands of original and printed botanical illustrations, educational plant models, and 2,500 unique glass plate negatives capturing the Garden's history, historic landscapes, and Belgium's colonial era in Central Africa. Apart from historical art work, the collection also includes contemporary botanical illustrations, including line drawings and watercolour paintings, created by artists from the Garden as well as external artists.

The library collection is fully catalogued and accessible online through our **library catalogue**, along with parts of the archives and art collection. Digitisation efforts focus on rare books, Garden publications, old photographs and selected archives, with materials available through platforms like Europeana, the Biodiversity Heritage Library, and Digital Archive Flanders. Together, these collections attract hundreds of visitors annually, serving as a centre for botanical research and heritage preservation.

Kniphoff, De Botanica in originali (1758-1764), one of the rare books of the library including plant images produced using the process called nature printing.

International partnerships and collaborations

Meise Botanic Garden plays an active role in global networks of herbaria and living collections, supporting collaborations at both national and international levels. Through these partnerships, the Garden helps facilitate the exchange of expertise, data, and resources, while promoting efficient use of funding and minimising duplication of efforts across organisations. As a member of organisations such as the Society for the Preservation of Natural History Collections (SPNHC) and the Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities (CETAF), the Garden contributes to the development and strengthening of these important networks.

CETAF has initiated several impactful projects, such as the SYNTHESIS(+) projects (2004-2023), which aimed to enhance access to European natural history collections by developing shared infrastructure, standardising best practices, and promoting joint research initiatives. They laid the foundation for the Distributed System of Scientific Collections (DiSSCo), a European Research Infrastructure with the vision to unify collections of more than 200 institutions across Europe into a single digital repository. These initiatives will be crucial for connecting collection data with other disciplines, such as genomics, climate science, remote sensing, and computational modelling, enabling interdisciplinary research and accelerating discoveries by eliminating barriers to data accessibility.

Achieving an integrated pan-European digital collection requires shared expertise in biodiversity informatics and emerging technologies such as machine learning. Developing and adhering to international Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) is essential for enabling data aggregation (e.g. through GBIF) and integration (e.g. through DiSSCo). Over the next decade, Meise Botanic Garden will further strengthen its involvement in these partnerships, and strive to become a global leader in all aspects of collection management, encompassing physical collection management, digitisation, and advancements in biodiversity informatics.

Building on our long-standing collaborations with Central African institutions, we aim to further expand our network to include underrepresented regions and institutions, with a particular focus on equitable partnerships in Central Africa and other regions. The practices of research overseas have undergone significant changes over recent decades. Historically, European taxonomic institutions often conducted research by collecting and archiving materials from overseas. This led to these collections, including critical type specimens, being housed in European institutions rather than in their native regions with easy access for local researchers. However, this approach has evolved substantially under frameworks such as the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and the Nagoya Protocol, emphasising collaboration with local partners and equitable benefit-sharing.

As a first step, we are intensifying efforts to provide access to digital collections and resources for overseas partners. Guided by the CARE principles, this approach seeks to redress accessibility issues to collections, and furthering research and conservation efforts in the originating countries, promoting sustainable and locally-driven initiatives.

Meise Botanic Garden is committed to advancing biodiversity research and conservation through capacity building and promoting the retention of future collections in their countries of origin. We actively contribute to initiatives such as the Global Taxonomy Initiative (GTI) and various capacity-building projects, while maintaining an editorial role in the *Abc Taxa* series to accelerate taxonomic training. Moreover, we collaborate with partners such as CIFOR, INERA, Kisangani University, and the Yangambi Research Centre to restore and digitise herbarium collections in Central Africa, creating a vital foundation for plant research in the region. Over the next decade, we aim to strengthen these partnerships further to develop, digitise, and unlock both herbarium and living collections in our partner institutions across Central Africa.

Science collections ambitions

Within the next ten years, the science collections of Meise Botanic Garden will increasingly reflect its dedication to scientific advancement and societal impact. Guided by the Garden's *Science Strategy*, *Living Collection Strategy*, and *Public Outreach Strategy*, these collections will continue to serve as vital resources for research, conservation, policy support, and public engagement, benefiting both the Garden and the global community.

The Garden will have strengthened its international leadership in plant research (spanning taxonomy to genomics), applied research (e.g. species identification and tracking illegal trading of plants and plant parts), biodiversity informatics including artificial intelligence, further reinforcing the significance of its collections. Due to its unique collections, the Garden has a pivotal role in the global network of botanic gardens and natural history museums.

The collections will be managed sustainably, adhering to the highest standards for both physical preservation and digital accessibility. Largely digitised, they will provide dynamic, open access resources for international research, integrating diverse data sources such as specimens, genetic data, and ecological information to support global research and conservation. The collections will inspire diverse audiences through public outreach, educational programs, citizen science programs, and collaborations with a variety of stakeholders, ensuring their continued societal relevance.

While each subcollection has unique characteristics, five ambitions will guide their development, preservation, and dissemination.

Collection development, research, conservation, and public engagement form a positive feedback loop, where each component strengthens the others in a continuous cycle of growth and impact. For instance, new research initiatives drive the expansion of collections and enrichment of their data, resulting in more comprehensive, well-documented collections that attract further research and public interest. In turn, citizen science efforts can contribute directly to collection enrichment, stimulating increased public engagement and support for ongoing research.

Ambition 1 - Strengthening the impact of our collections for research, conservation, and policymaking

To ensure the continued relevance of our collections, their development will be guided by criteria that reflect the Garden's historical strengths and align with its *Science Strategy* and institutional mission.

The Garden will prioritise taxonomic groups and geographical regions where it has established significant expertise and extensive collections in the past. This focus aims to preserve the international distinctiveness of the collections while keeping them dynamic and responsive to emerging research trends, conservation priorities, and policy needs. Historically, scientific research at Meise Botanic Garden has been closely linked to the expansion of its collections, creating a positive feedback loop where comprehensive, well-documented collections attract further research. This approach will continue to guide collection enrichment, promoting collaborations within the Garden and with external partners.

Our library houses a world-class collection of historic and contemporary literature, serving as a vital resource for botanical research. To maintain its relevance and accessibility, we will refine our acquisition strategies in collaboration with research institutions in Flanders and globally, while focusing on digitisation, text mining, and the curation of digital literature (see Ambition 3).

New technologies, such as DNA sequencing from

herbarium specimens and artificial intelligence for large-scale phenotypic data analysis, present opportunities to unlock the potential of existing collections at an accelerated rate. Although most new acquisitions in recent decades have come from gifts and exchanges that may not align with our priorities, strategic acquisitions and targeted field expeditions conducted by Garden staff remain crucial. New collections are vital not only for current research, but also for creating and maintaining reference material and 'measuring points' over time, enabling future studies on biodiversity changes and plant responses through different periods. Overseas expeditions will prioritise partnerships with local collaborators, ensuring original materials are deposited in-country whenever feasible, while also supporting the development of local infrastructure for collection storage and curation.

The collections not only underpin the Garden's research and conservation efforts but also serve as critical resources for other institutions worldwide. The development strategy must therefore reflect the uniqueness and quality of the collections (ensuring the physical integrity of specimens and the completeness of collection data), while emphasising their global importance and alignment with international research priorities.

The Garden's *Science Strategy* identifies several ambitions to address urgent global challenges, including biodiversity loss, climate change, and food security. These ambitions are deeply reliant on our collections. Efforts in collection development and prioritisation will align with these goals while ensuring the collections continue to support a broad range of scientific and societal needs. Below, we elaborate on each science ambition and outline the corresponding collection priorities that will underpin them.

Our scientific research is deeply rooted in and reliant upon our collections, with our different sub-collections serving multiple research themes.

Safeguarding the Belgian flora and contributing to global conservation challenges

Biodiversity is globally threatened by habitat destruction, pollution, climate change, and overharvesting. Meise Botanic Garden aims to address these issues through global cooperation, innovative strategies, and its expertise in monitoring and conserving vulnerable species, particularly in tropical Africa and Europe, while developing evidence-based strategies for in situ and ex situ conservation, including reintroduction and reinforcement programs, to strengthen ecosystem resilience in Belgium.

Collection priorities

- The **seed bank** plays a vital role in conserving plant genetic diversity. Over the next decade, we will expand collaborations with Belgian and international partners, building on the success of current seed collection and reintroduction projects while initiating new initiatives to further strengthen the conservation of plant species. Seed bank priorities are detailed in the *Living Collections Strategy*.
- Our **living plant collections**, both indoor and outdoor, will continue to prioritise the ex situ conservation of IUCN red listed species, including threatened Belgian flora. Priorities for the living plant collection are detailed in the *Living Collections Strategy*.
- We will prioritise the integration of **herbarium**, **molecular**, and **living collections** to support research on genetic diversity, population structure, and evolutionary potential, guiding strategies for resilience and extinction prevention (in line with the development of metacollections in the *Living Collection Strategy*). Molecular samples will be collected from living accessions and seeds to document their genetic diversity.
- The **library** and **archives** provide access to historical records, floristic studies, and ecological data, enabling a better understanding of trends in the Belgian flora.

Taking on global change challenges for plant diversity

This science ambition focuses on understanding biodiversity changes, species interactions, and invasive species spread under global change. By utilising collection data and biodiversity informatics, we monitor species distributions, traits, and ecological dynamics to assess threats, inform policy, and mitigate human impacts such as pollution. Additionally, we are developing methods to track plant materials and combat illegal trade.

Collection priorities

- We will enhance our **herbarium collection** with recent specimens, precise geographic data, and accurate species identifications to support research on historical and current changes in species distributions, traits, phenology, and population genetics.

- We will expand our **molecular collection** to support DNA-based biodiversity research, including species identification, population genetics, and environmental DNA analysis.
- We will strengthen collections of **wood** and **economically important plants**, especially coffee and cacao, to provide reference materials for chemical and genetic analyses, enabling tracing and identification of plant materials in illegal trade.
- We will utilise and integrate **biodiversity data** from diverse sources (Collections, literature, field observations, remote sensing, molecular data, archives, etc.) combined with environmental data to analyse the impacts of global change on biodiversity. We will invest in biodiversity informatics expertise to manage, analyse, and store these datasets, offering actionable insights and tools for policymakers.
- We will digitise **library** and **archives** collections to unlock valuable data on biodiversity, enhancing accessibility for research and policy development.

Contributing to food and health security

Research on plant genetic resources is important for tackling global food security challenges. Over the next decade, we will expand studies on crop wild relatives, including edible mushrooms. Additionally, we plan to establish a network in Flanders for conserving local crop and wild genetic resources.

Collection priorities

- Our expanding **living** and **seed collections** of crop wild relatives, including wild bananas, wild beans, and coffee, are crucial for preserving genetic diversity and provide critical resources for research. We aim to extend this collection with local crop and wild genetic resources through the establishment of a network in Flanders to conserve regional genetic diversity. Priorities for the living and seed collections are detailed in the *Living Collections Strategy*.
- **Living strains of edible fungi** represent a future focus for collection development. With the planned launch of projects centred on fungi cultivation in tropical Africa, we aim to establish strain collections from the field under secure conditions. Each wild strain will be preserved in partner laboratories within its country of origin, with a back-up stored at the Garden. This yet-to-be-developed fungal strain collection will ensure the continuity of programs to conserve and promote African edible mushrooms, one of the institution's core businesses.
- The **herbarium** and **molecular** collection support research on the diversity and evolutionary relationships of crop wild relatives and tropical edible mushrooms. By improving the quality of their historical and geographical data, we can analyse shifts in species distribution and adaptability, revealing how these species can strengthen agricultural resilience and sustainable food production in the face of climate change.

Understanding and recording biodiversity

This priority combines taxonomy, evolutionary studies, and ecological research to enhance our understanding of plant biodiversity and its role in ecosystem sustainability. Taxonomy provides baseline data for biodiversity research. Molecular data are transforming taxonomy by uncovering complex evolutionary histories of plants, providing more precise species boundaries and producing classifications that more accurately reflect evolutionary relationships. Biogeographical research uncovers patterns of plant diversification, while studies on trait evolution, adaptation, and speciation reveal how organisms respond to environmental changes and how new species emerge. Large-scale biodiversity studies, including reconstructing the Tree of Life and global biodiversity patterns, require extensive sampling across diverse taxa and regions. Future research will increasingly involve collaborations with international institutions and consortia, with partner institutions contributing to collections and sampling efforts.

Collection priorities

- We will build upon our historic **herbarium** collections while pursuing targeted new collection efforts. Our expertise in key taxonomic groups, including Rubiaceae (coffee family), Poaceae (grasses), Balsaminaceae, Fabaceae (legumes), fungi, lichens, diatoms, macroalgae, and myxomycetes, will continue to guide the development of our collections. As taxonomic gaps and emerging research opportunities are identified, future efforts will increasingly focus on groups of **policy and conservation concern**. These include indicator species, invasive species, endangered species, harmful species, pollinator hosts, crop wild relatives, and taxa relevant to the European habitat and water framework directives, aquaculture, and other economically significant areas.
- We will expand **molecular collections** to support modern biodiversity research, emphasising their integration with voucher herbarium specimens to strengthen DNA-based taxonomy and molecular phylogenetics.
- We will combine **living collections**, herbarium specimens, and molecular data to advance taxonomic research. The living collections complement preserved specimens, particularly for groups where morphological characteristics are difficult to preserve, such as succulents. Our living succulent collections, among the largest in the world, include many type clones and will be further developed over the next decade.
- Our **library** remains an essential resource, housing rare and underrepresented literature that supports taxonomic research. Digitisation initiatives will be key to unlock taxonomic information.

Central African herbarium: a sound taxonomic foundation with expanding potential

The Central African herbarium, comprising over 600,000 plant specimens, is one of the most significant globally. It dates back to Belgian colonial times, laying the foundation for pioneering taxonomic studies by botanists such as Théophile Durand and Émile De Wildeman. In 1934, the Congo herbarium from the Royal Museum for Central Africa was added to the collection. Ongoing taxonomic research has produced major works such as *Flore d'Afrique centrale* and *Flore du Gabon*, alongside detailed studies of families such as Rubiaceae and Balsaminaceae. Recent findings highlight the incompleteness of botanical exploration in tropical Africa and emphasise the need for intensified collection efforts. Plans to develop dynamic eFlora portals for tropical African countries aim to create an interactive platform that combines collection data, taxonomic information, images, and maps, improving global accessibility and connectivity to the region's biodiversity.

Beyond taxonomy, the collection supports a wide array of new research initiatives. Spatio-temporal specimen data aid IUCN Red List assessments, while trait, associated micro-organisms, and biochemical analyses reveal plant responses to climate change. Genomic analyses of specimens advance understanding of species diversity and population dynamics on the African continent. Applied research includes genetic and chemical studies of crop wild relatives such as coffee and wild beans, and the tracing of commodities such as wood, coffee, and cacao to combat illegal trade. These applications merely scratch the surface of the collection's potential. Future opportunities include studying invasive species, monitoring rare plants, exploring pollination ecology, and bioprospecting natural resources.

Belgian herbarium: from floristics to climate change research

The Belgian herbarium, containing nearly half a million specimens, is among the earliest collections of the Garden, established shortly after the founding of the Jardin botanique de l'État. A milestone in its development was acquiring François Crépin's extensive collection, which has been instrumental in Belgian floristic studies and continues to support the *Flora of Belgium and Luxembourg*. It also serves as a major reference for non-indigenous plants in Belgium, contributing to the Garden's online platform, *Manual of the Alien Plants of Belgium*.

The herbarium and the archives are vital resources for historical distribution data, trait analyses, and global change research. The FOURCAST project, for instance, utilises the collection to study shifts

in species composition and functional traits, linking these changes to climate models. This work informs forest management and urban planning strategies to mitigate biodiversity loss and improve ecosystem functioning.

The Belgian herbarium will remain vital for both traditional floristic studies and emerging research fields, such as population genomics, conservation science, and environmental monitoring. It also plays a key role in education and citizen science initiatives, and is therefore of continued relevance for research and public engagement.

Plant collecting in the coastal dunes near Nieuwpoort during an excursion of the Société royale de Botanique de Belgique in 1891 (François Crépin is seen on the left, with pipe). Several participants carry a vasculum in which they store the plants they collect during the excursion. Photo (glass plate #0158): Meise Botanic Garden, Library.

Mycological collection: fungal diversity discovery and future innovation

Meise Botanic Garden has a long-standing tradition in mycological research. The early collection of Martha Goossens-Fontana from Central Africa served as the basis for research on tropical fungi, including the publication of the *Fungus Flora of Tropical Africa* (www.FFTA-online.org). Over time, the collection has expanded to cover Belgium, Europe, and Southeast Asia. Mycological research at the Garden remains very active, employing modern taxonomic and phylogenetic approaches, including DNA-based studies. The focus has partially shifted towards documenting the diversity of edible fungi in tropical Africa (www.EFTA-online.org) and understanding the ecosystem services they provide. This work is closely linked to North-South partner-

ships, the preservation of traditional knowledge, and capacity-building initiatives in the partner countries. The fungal collection also underpins identification services, which we aim to expand in the coming decade. The collections will continue to support research in fungal biodiversity, evolutionary research, and conservation. Emerging opportunities include studies on speciation, climate change modelling, and support to local populations in cultivating local edible species. This highlights the collection's role in advancing our understanding of fungal diversity, and addressing ecological and societal challenges.

Lichen collection: advancing taxonomy, phylogenetics, and environmental monitoring

Meise Botanic Garden houses one of the most significant collections of Western European lichens, thanks to the recent acquisitions of the private herbaria from André Aptroot and Pieter van den Boom. These collections also include numerous specimens from across the tropics. Additionally, it is recognised as one of the world's most important collections of lichenicolous fungi (fungi that live on lichen), particularly following the recent acquisition of Paul Diederich's herbarium, which contains a large number of type specimens. This collection serves as the primary resource for the ongoing *Flora of Lichenicolous Fungi*. Both historical collections and recent fieldwork have expanded the herbarium with African specimens, from mainland Africa as well as islands such as Madagascar, Mayotte, Mauritius, and Macaronesia. These collections

are used for taxonomic and phylogenetic works and checklists. The herbarium also places a strong emphasis on Belgium, supporting floristic studies and enhancing our understanding of the evolution of its fungi in relation to air pollution, forest management, and climate change. Moreover, the lichen collection serves as a crucial reference database for secondary metabolites, supporting species identification through thin-layer chromatography analyses. Future efforts will focus on enlarging the lichen collection for Western Europe and the tropics, in particular Africa, as well as expanding the collection of lichenicolous fungi.

Diatom collection: from taxonomy to water quality monitoring

The diatom collection of Meise Botanic Garden ranks among the ten largest in the world. It includes the historic 19th-century Van Heurck collection (transferred from the museum at the former botanical garden in Antwerp to Meise Botanic Garden in 2006), as well as extensive African and polar diatom collections. The Van Heurck collection, comprising both microscope slides and unmounted diatom material, contains important gatherings made by renowned researchers such as Smith, Delogne, Grunow, Walker-Arnott, Kützing, Rabenhorst, and Van Heurck himself, including hundreds of original type materials. The African collection contains a large number of samples mainly collected from Senegal, Tchad, Democratic Republic of the Congo, and Tanzania. The polar diatom collection, arguably the largest of its kind, focuses on freshwater diatoms

from the Antarctic and Arctic realm with thousands of samples from the sub-Antarctic islands, Greenland, and Svalbard. Each year, the historic collection attracts international scientists who use it for taxonomic research whereas the African and polar collections offer interesting contributions to ecological, paleo-ecological, and biogeographical research. In the next decade, the diatom collection will continue to play an important role in diatom identification services applied in biodiversity and water quality monitoring, training of new diatomists, and improvement of our knowledge of diatom systematics.

The herbarium holds one of the most extensive collections of marine macroalgae from the Indian-West Pacific region. This collection supports research on the diversity, biogeography, and evolutionary history of green, brown, and red seaweeds, with recent studies emphasising taxa significant to aquaculture.

Myxomycetes, or slime moulds, are eukaryotic organisms historically classified as but unrelated to fungi. They play key roles in nutrient cycling and ecosystem dynamics. Meise Botanic Garden's myxomycetes collection includes about 40,000 specimens, supporting research on their taxonomy, diversity, and potential applications in biocontrol of plant pathogens.

Wood collection: from historical specimens to tracing of timber origins

The wood collection is a unique resource comprising more than 10,000 samples from Europe, the Americas, Asia, and tropical Africa, dating back to the 19th century. It also includes materials from the former forestry museum, as well as a historically significant collection of wood samples from around the world from Karel Edward Frison (1888-1973), which was recently relocated from Antwerp to Meise Botanic Garden. A link between the specimens from the wood collection in the AfricaMuseum at Tervuren and our herbarium specimens enables integrated research on trees and their ecological contexts. Advances in biochemical and molecular

analyses, supported by georeferenced samples and AI-driven spatial models, have expanded the research potential of this collection. These tools enable precise tracing of wood origins, which is critical for supporting efforts to combat illegal logging and support sustainable forest management. As a consortium partner of World Forest ID, the Garden contributes to the development of these traceability systems for timber and other forest products. Through these new developments, our wood collection will significantly expand in the future, incorporating new samples from Europe and around the world to serve as reference materials.

Goals by 2035

- The international uniqueness of our collections is strengthened by prioritising taxonomic groups and regions where we have a historical focus, as well as collections that play pivotal roles in addressing biodiversity loss, climate change, and food security.
- Our collections include a global reference set of wood specimens for tree species threatened by international trade.
- Molecular samples are gathered from living accessions to document their genetic diversity.
- A long-term collection policy is in place for the library, archives, and art collection, emphasising an acquisition strategy and a plan to enhance digital accessibility to online literature.

Ambition 2 - Securing the collections for future generations

The Garden's research ambitions are both timely and enduring, with their relevance expected to persist for future generations. Therefore, it is crucial to safeguard the long-term preservation of our collections critical global resources. Our commitment to high-quality curation, strengthened partnerships, compliance with international regulations, and upgraded infrastructure ensures that Meise Botanic Garden's physical and digital resources remain invaluable for global research, conservation, and public engagement for decades to come.

Building a state-of-the-art infrastructure

The Meise Botanic Garden's masterplan prioritises the development of modern and sustainable collection, research, and tourism infrastructures. In the initial phases, significant progress has been made with the renovation and construction of glasshouses, the establishment of thematic gardens, and the enhancement of seed bank infrastructure. The next phase includes the creation of a new research campus, designed to include secure, long-term storage facilities for the preserved collections.

A new research campus

The current facilities housing the herbarium and library collections, constructed in the 1950s and 1980s, require significant upgrades. In particular, the older building is in urgent need of renovation. To minimise environmental impact, we will focus on renovation rather than rebuilding, preserving the modernist architectural design while enhancing insulation and technical systems to meet contemporary standards.

The new campus will provide state-of-the-art facilities to house collections and support staff, including researchers, collection managers, and administrative staff. Secure, climate-controlled storage rooms will preserve the herbarium, library, archives, and art collections for future generations.

Compact and adaptable storage systems will maximise space efficiency and accommodate projected expansion needs for the next 60 years, positioning the Garden as a safe haven for collections from other institutions or private donors. The campus will also feature clean rooms and laboratory spaces for the study and curation of specimens and literature, advanced digitisation infrastructure, and cutting-edge research facilities, along with a conference room, educational spaces and an exhibition area.

Construction is set to begin in 2028, with completion expected by 2031, transforming Meise Botanic Garden into a state-of-the-art research hub.

Credit: Robbrecht en Daem architecten.

Integrating international best practices in collection management

Over the next decade, we will prioritise the adoption, enhancement, and integration of international best practices in collection management, including environmental control and pest management. These practices will be formalised into tailored collection policies for the various subcollections. We will align with and actively contribute to guidelines and standards established by Botanic Gardens Conservation International (BGCI), SPNHC, and the DiSSCo infrastructure, as well as those developed through past and future European collaborative projects.

For the library and archives, we will adopt best practices in physical collection management, restoration, and digital preservation by maintaining strong collaborations and sharing expertise with national partners such as the Royal Library of Belgium and Digital Archive Flanders, and international networks such as the European Botanical and Horticultural Libraries Group, the Council on Botanical and Horticultural Libraries, Europeana, Archives Portal Europe, and the Biodiversity Heritage Library. A new policy will be developed and implemented for the preservation of botanical drawings and watercolour painting made by the Garden's staff.

The molecular collection will be fully integrated into our collection management system, following best practices established through initiatives such as SYNTHESYS+ and DiSSCo Flanders.

Legal and ethical compliance will remain important. We will uphold national and international agreements around the use of local biological resources, including the Nagoya Protocol, CARE principles, CITES, and phytosanitary regulations. These commitments will ensure the integrity of our collections while promoting inclusivity and transparency.

Securing long-term preservation of collection data

Over the next decade, we will standardise collection data within a unified Collection Management System (CMS), EarthCape, for our living plant collections, seed bank, herbarium, and molecular collections. This will enhance data accuracy, usability, and accessibility while streamlining workflows such as loan services, and facilitating data publication in adherence to biodiversity data standards. Integrating collection data with other sources, such as taxonomic information, genetic data, images, literature, and more, will further enrich our collection data. Our new CMS will also enhance the efficiency of collecting expeditions by enabling researchers to directly input collection data, along with field observations and photographs, enhancing the overall value and richness of the collections. This streamlined approach will not only increase the value of our collections but also facilitate integration with ongoing initiatives to develop eFlora portals, particularly for tropical African countries. Integrating all collection data into one system will also support compliance with legal obligations by incorporating the legal and contractual typologies developed under the SYNTHESYS+ project, ensuring interoperability with future DiSSCo systems. Future developments include integrating a dynamic taxonomic data backbone, creating a mobile app for collection management, and enabling collection managers to monitor and report on collection status through key performance indicators.

We will invest in secure digital storage solutions for collection data and images combining in-house servers with deep storage, in partnership with specialised companies such as Meemoo. Recognising the growing importance of genomic studies, we will establish methods for curating and storing high-throughput sequencing libraries.

Detailed collection policies for each subcollection will be updated or developed to implement best practices in digital data preservation. An institution-wide Data Management Plan (DMP) will guide digital collection management, incorporating international data standards (TDWG) to ensure interoperability and global visibility. This DMP will provide clarity on data management practices and responsibilities, serving as a key resource for collection managers and researchers.

Molecular collection: from lab collections to globally interconnected data

The molecular collection, a recent addition, supports phylogenetic and evolutionary research but has, to date, been minimally integrated within our other collections. This will change with the implementation of a new collection management system that will incorporate the molecular collection. Recent European projects, such as SYNTHESIS+, and the efforts of the DiSSCo Flanders molecular collection working group, have provided essential guidelines for the effective management of molecular collections. As active participants in these projects, we are committed to adopting their recommendations to establish a structured and standardised approach to physical and digital collection management.

This strategy will ensure the collection's preservation, accessibility, and relevance over the next decade. Key efforts include aligning the molecular collection with global networks such as the Global Genome Biodiversity Network (GGBN), and international anchorage with the International Barcode of Life project (iBOL), iBOL Europe, and the Barcode of Life Data Systems (BOLD) to enhance its visibility and promote international collaboration.

Ensuring the continuation of collection expertise and knowledge

Over the years, we have built substantial expertise in collection management (including database management, digitisation technologies, and biodiversity informatics) as well as in taxonomic and molecular research, which are crucial for the accurate identification and interpretation of our collections. This specialised knowledge is critical to maintaining the integrity, accessibility, and utility of our collections. Ensuring the continuation of this expertise is a priority, not only to support internal operations but also to benefit the broader scientific community.

Over the next decade, we will prioritise documentation of collection expertise, and make this knowledge findable and accessible, both internally and to external collaborators. This effort will safeguard institutional knowledge against potential loss due to personnel changes while promoting knowledge-sharing and collaboration across the global collections community.

Goals by 2035

- A new research and collection campus will be completed with secure, climate-controlled storage facilities for herbarium specimens, library materials, and archival collections.
- Modular and compact storage systems maximise space efficiency and allow for 60 years of expansion, establishing the Garden as a secure repository for collections from institutions and private donors.
- A unified Collection Management System (CMS) is in place, integrating the living plant collections, seed bank, herbarium, and molecular collections, applying a single taxonomic backbone, and ensuring clear documentation of permits and restrictions.

Ambition 3 - Expanding global access to our collections and their data

Over the next decade, we will implement new strategies to further enhance the accessibility of our collections, both physically and digitally. By adopting innovative biodiversity information approaches and developing advanced technologies such as machine learning, we aim to broaden access and maximise the impact of our collections for the research community. These efforts aim to expand access and maximise the impact of our collections for research, education, and decision-making, aligning with the Global Strategy for Plant Conservation to make biodiversity data and collections widely available through digitisation and online platforms. The digital accessibility of our collections also contributes to the open data objectives within the framework of the EOSC initiative of the European Commission and the Flemish Research Data Network (FRDN) and Flemish Open Science Board (FOSB).

Expand digital access

Scientific collections and literature often face challenges of limited findability and accessibility, requiring researchers to request physical loans (posing risks of damage or loss) or travel to find and access materials. These barriers hinder efficient use and limit the impact of collections. To address these issues, digitisation initiatives and international infrastructures such as GBIF and DiSSCo are creating unified digital repositories, significantly enhancing access. The emerging Digital Extended Specimen (DES) concept further expands the utility of collections by linking digital representations of specimens to diverse data sources, enabling interdisciplinary research. Meise Botanic Garden has been a pioneer in digitisation, with nearly three million of its estimated four million herbarium specimens now accessible online via its collection portal (botanicalcollections.be) and GBIF, including 2.5 million with high-resolution images. However, significant gaps remain, such as the mycological, lichenological, bryophyte, myxomycete, wood, economic botany, and diatom collections. Digitisation is

Unlocking botanical knowledge

The library and archives of Meise Botanic Garden are vital repositories of botanical knowledge, supporting research, education, and conservation. Our collections of journals, books, and archival materials are central to advancing biodiversity studies. Through digitisation, we aim to enhance global accessibility by collaborating with initiatives such as the Biodiversity Heritage Library and Plazi.

In the coming decade, we will use biodiversity informatics and AI to extract and interlink data from taxonomic literature. Projects such as BiCICKL, TETTRiS, and DiSSCo Flanders highlight our efforts to connect specimens with taxonomic, phenotypic,

and genetic information. Using XML-based systems and machine learning, we aim to enhance the discoverability and usability of botanical data across platforms such as GBIF, World Flora Online, Treatment Bank, and the European Nucleotide Archive.

By applying innovative technologies and adhering to FAIR principles, we aim to unlock data from literature and link these to collections. This will advance taxonomy and other fields such as conservation genetics and trait analysis, and will position the Garden as a leader in digital botanical research.

an ongoing effort, involving georeferencing and enriching data with taxonomic insights.

Certain special collections present unique challenges for digitisation, such as photographing specimens preserved in liquid or microscope slides, which require further development. Additionally, some specimens, such as diatom samples, often contain multiple species, differing from classical herbarium specimens where a single species is typically represented. To address these complexities, we are developing data models to accurately capture this information in our new CSM, EarthCape. Our new CMS will further simplify data publication to the botanicalcollections.be platform and international platforms like GBIF and the future DiSSCo data store.

Over the next decade, advancing the FAIR principles for collection data will be a priority. Within the DiSSCo Flanders projects and the European DiSSCo Research Infrastructure, we will contribute to developing services such as a unified loans and visits system and a centralised platform for collaborative curation and annotation. To ensure optimal integration with DiSSCo, we will adhere to and further develop international data standards like Darwin Core and the International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF). As the leader of DiSSCo Flanders and the DiSSCo FWB consortium, we will collaborate with major collection-holding institutions in Flanders and Belgium to improve accessibility and interoperability.

The entire library of Meise Botanic Garden, along with parts of the archives and art collections, is accessible through our online catalogue, as well as through the Union Catalogue of Belgian Libraries (UniCat). Targeted digitisation efforts are underway, with a current focus on rare books and publications published by the Garden, as well as selected archives and art collections. These digitised materials are made openly accessible on our online catalogue, on Europeana, and through collaboration with the Biodiversity Heritage Library, Archives Portal Europe, and Digital Archive Flanders. We will evaluate the sustainability and adaptability of our catalogue system, VUBIS, to modern standards and emerging technologies. We will also explore collaborations with scientific institutions and universities in Flanders to improve access to digital literature and monitor open access developments.

To accelerate digital collection management and analysis, we will explore machine learning applications for tasks such as label transcription, data cleaning, specimen segmentation, trait analysis, and data interconnection. These technologies will streamline curation, enhance data quality, and expand research opportunities.

An exquisite illustration of *Epidendrum paniculatum*, featured in *Lindenia: Iconographie des Orchidées (1885)* by Linden et al., one of the rare books from the Garden's library now accessible through the Biodiversity Heritage Library.

The digital extended specimen

The pan-European research infrastructure DiSSCo aims to maximise the potential of Natural Science Collections by unifying all collections into one comprehensive digital repository, minting persistent Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) for each individual specimen.

The cornerstone of the DiSSCo infrastructure is the concept of the digital extended specimen (DES), which serves as a force multiplier by enabling innovative ways of interacting with collections. In a DES, the physical specimen is augmented by a "digital twin" that incorporates collection data, taxonomic information, and a scanned image of the specimen. Using information technology, DES's can establish machine-readable connections to various types of derived and associated data such as DNA sequences, trait data, field and living plant photographs, and taxonomic treatments in the literature.

By using persistent identifiers, a DES can be transformed into a FAIR digital representation of a specimen, allowing unambiguous citation. A DES will be machine-actionable, facilitating more effective annotation, enrichment, and curation of collection data. This transformation of specimen data will enable the integration of diverse data types and will simplify data sharing among institutions and information systems. It will also enable the development of e-services such as a centralised European Loans and Visits System, a unified annotation system and a Collection Digitisation Dashboard.

The DES framework has great potential for scientific research. Researchers will benefit from improved accessibility and annotation options, while data integration will facilitate exploration of interconnected research questions, enabling collaborative and interdisciplinary studies.

While the concept of the DES is well defined, its practical implementation is still in its early stages. Key knowledge gaps that need to be addressed for future development include establishing a linked open data framework, developing curation and annotation systems, advancing AI technologies to enable automation, and how to deal with sensitive information, such as locality data for endangered species, and a global patchwork of access and benefit sharing policies.

Improve physical access

In certain situations, examining collections on-site is essential or beneficial, such as when dealing with fragile or rare specimens or literature, when large quantities of specimens require study, or when direct collaboration with curators or researchers is needed. Our new facilities will be designed to optimise the experience of scientific visitors, students, and interns, offering modern laboratories and shared spaces equipped with advanced microscopy, molecular labs, and digitisation tools, as well as a dedicated reading room to consult literature and archives. These shared spaces will facilitate interactions between visiting scientists and staff of Meise Botanic Garden, promoting knowledge exchange and collaboration. Dedicated guest rooms within the Garden enhance the comfort and convenience of international scientific visitors.

To enhance access, we will review and simplify the procedures for requesting visits and loans, providing guidelines and implementing an efficient access system. In collaboration with DiSSCo, we will contribute to the development of a unified European loans and visits system, making collections more accessible to the broader scientific community. By continuing our digitisation efforts, we enable researchers to target relevant collections more quickly, increasing the efficiency and impact of their work.

Goals by 2035

- All remaining collections of fungi, bryophytes, lichens, wood, diatoms, and economic botany will be fully digitised.
- We have improved methods to document and track the collections' reach and scientific impact by monitoring key indicators such as scientific visitor numbers, online engagement, loan requests, and collection-based publications.
- We have developed solutions for digitising special collections, including liquid-preserved specimens and microscopic slides.
- The implementation of the new CMS (EarthCape) has streamlined data publication processes to our collection portal and global platforms (e.g. GBIF).
- Machine learning technologies have been developed and applied to accelerate collection curation and improve data interoperability.
- Active participation in the development of DiSSCo's research infrastructure and adherence to international standards and interoperability frameworks has resulted in the inclusion of the Garden's collections in a unified, interoperable network for biodiversity data.
- Meise Botanic Garden has become a central hub for digital natural science collections in Flanders, leading initiatives in accessibility and innovation.
- The library has digitised all works published by the Garden, along with key portions of its most important holdings, including rare books and Belgian and Central African botanical literature and resources.
- Collaborations with scientific institutions and universities in Flanders have improved access to digital literature.

Ambition 4 - Engaging the public with biodiversity through collections

As a tourist destination, Meise Botanic Garden attracts more than 250,000 visitors annually. Through its outdoor plant displays, glasshouses, exhibits, and landscaped domain, visitors can engage with the rich diversity of plant life, cultivating greater appreciation and awareness of the critical role plants play in our ecosystems and daily lives. A notable recent addition has been the WOODLab, which presents the Garden's rich wood collection and emphasises the importance of wood as a sustainable natural resource. The Garden will further enhance public engagement with its extensive collections and research.

Currently, three thematic storylines (soon to be joined by two more) highlight various aspects of the Garden's work, including its historical gardens, global flora and biomes, the significance of plants for humans, plant relationships, and plant conservation. Over the next decade, the Garden will develop a sixth storyline, the "The Botanic Garden, a treasure trove", to be housed in the renovated research and collection campus. This storyline will provide visitors with an engaging insight into the collections and the scientific research they support. This interactive exhibit will explore the journeys of historically important botanists and emphasise the significance of modern collection-based research. Key collections featured will include the herbarium (including its Economic Botany Collection), the library, archives, and art collection.

Meise Botanic Garden will further expand its reach by combining physical exhibitions with virtual platforms such as Europeana, making the collections accessible to a wider audience. The library will also be redesigned to improve public access, offering a dedicated reading room where visitors can engage with specialised staff to explore its resources.

To promote public involvement with the collections, the Garden—through the DiSSCo Flanders projects—will invest in its own cutting-edge crowdsourcing platforms, Doe-Dat, and continue its participation in international initiatives such as WeDigBio, a global event that promotes the digitisation of natural history collections.

The Garden is committed to strengthening its educational outreach, public engagement initiatives, and citizen science activities as outlined in our *Public Outreach Strategy* and *Science Strategy*. These efforts will inspire greater public appreciation for plants and biodiversity.

The WOODlab experience. The WOODlab, which opened its doors in 2019, showcases the Garden's extensive wood collection and emphasises the importance of wood as a sustainable natural resource. It is a good example of how we have used our collections in an innovative and interactive exhibition that appeals to the public.

Economic Botany Collection: stories of plants and possibilities. The collection comprises around 25,000 items including wood samples, fibres, dyes, essential oils, and medicinal substances. Mostly gathered overseas including former colonies during the 19th and early 20th centuries, this collection reflects a period of intense exploration of natural products, driven by scientific curiosity and economic interests. Showcasing historical uses of plants, it will feature in the upcoming "Treasury" exhibition.

The extensive library, archives, and art collection serve as the foundation for exhibitions held within and outside the Garden, as well as virtual exhibitions on the Europeana website. Previous exhibitions have explored topics such as the history of the Garden, botanical expeditions, and notable collections and researchers, including François Crépin and his study of wild roses. This figure was featured in the "Plant Hunters" exhibition, which showed the 19th-century emergence of

Belgian plant collectors and the growth of horticulture in Belgium. Our collection includes many more treasures, such as glass negatives of past Belgian landscapes, rare botanical drawings and watercolour paintings, botanical models, and untapped archives. These resources will inspire and shape captivating exhibitions in the future.

Engaging the public in specimen transcription

The digitisation of collections is a huge and resource-intensive task. To help address this challenge, Meise Botanic Garden has developed DoeDat, a multilingual crowdsourcing platform that engages the public in the transcription of herbarium specimen labels. As part of DiSSCo Flanders, DoeDat is undergoing significant redevelopment to enhance its security, flexibility, and interoperability by adopting modern standards, including IIIF.

We envisage DoeDat as a European-scale service within the DiSSCo research infrastructure. The updated platform will support a broader array of digital objects, ranging from biodiversity specimens

to historical archives, while providing advanced functionalities.

By engaging a global volunteer community, DoeDat accelerates digitisation efforts, reduces costs, and facilitates the extraction of enriched data, including ecological and trait-related information. This enhances the scientific utility of collections while promoting public involvement in biodiversity research. The platform demonstrates the potential of citizen science to generate high-quality data and promote a connection between the public and scientific research.

Goals by 2035

- The Garden has enhanced public access to its preserved collections through a newly developed permanent exhibition and a series of temporary exhibitions that highlight the significance of these collections for research and society.
- The Garden has improved the presentation of its collections on its website, making them more accessible to both the general public and specialists.
- DoeDat, our crowdsourcing platform, has grown into a European-scale service within DiSSCo, mobilising a global volunteer community to accelerate data transcription and enhance public engagement in scientific research.

Ambition 5 - Strengthening our position as a global centre of excellence in collections and data

A key partner in the DiSSCo infrastructure

Meise Botanic Garden is an active member of CETAF and a leading contributor to European projects focused on improving access to natural history collections. These initiatives include the SYNTHESYS projects and DiSSCo, a European Research Infrastructure designed to unify the collections of over 200 institutions into a single digital repository.

Realising this vision depends on expertise in biodiversity informatics, emerging technologies such as machine

learning, and adherence to international Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) to facilitate data aggregation and integration.

As the coordinator of DiSSCo Flanders and DiSSCo FWB, a consortium of major collection-holding institutions in Belgium, the Garden will play a crucial role in advancing DiSSCo's goals and integrating regional expertise into the European framework.

Over the next decade, the Garden will further strengthen its contributions, utilising its expertise in collection management, digitisation, and biodiversity informatics to support the development and success of the European DiSSCo infrastructure.

DiSSCo Flanders: digitally uniting Flanders' natural science collections for global accessibility

Natural science collections are remarkably diverse, encompassing living and preserved specimens of animals, plants, and fungi, their molecular samples, and geological and soil collections. These collections have provided critical insights into life and earth sciences, yet many remain underutilised due to limited findability and accessibility.

The European Research Infrastructure DiSSCo (Distributed System of Scientific Collections) aims to address this challenge by digitally unifying all European natural history collections. By adhering to FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), DiSSCo aims to transform the currently fragmented landscape of collections into

a cohesive, interconnected knowledge base. This initiative will enable researchers to access and integrate data from diverse collections, providing new opportunities for scientific discovery, innovation, and biodiversity conservation.

Meise Botanic Garden coordinates DiSSCo Flanders, as well as DiSSCo FWB, which play crucial roles in the European DiSSCo infrastructure. The consortium includes all major natural science collection-holding institutions in Flanders, such as universities, research institutions, botanical gardens, and arboreta (VBTA), along with associated federal institutions and French-speaking universities.

Through projects funded by the Research Foundation – Flanders (FWO), we integrate Flanders’ rich and diverse collections on a single portal (discoflanders.be) and ensure their long-term preservation. All Belgian botanical collections are being made accessible through the botanicalcollections.be portal. We advance digital collection management through innovative approaches such as biodiversity informatics and artificial intelligence, linking physical specimens with their digital representations across infrastructures. Additionally, we enhance citizen engagement through a cutting-edge crowdsourcing platform DoeDat. These efforts will strengthen DiSSCo’s services and elevate the visibility and use of Flemish (and Belgian) collections and expertise on a global scale.

The Garden’s core activities, including preservation, digitisation, and databasing its collections form the foundation for advancing the goals of DiSSCo Flanders. Building on this foundation, DiSSCo Flanders focuses on digital innovation, data integration, and international collaboration by incorporating advanced technologies such as machine learning and adhering to FAIR principles. These combined efforts support interdisciplinary research, address socio-economic challenges such as global change and food security, and establish Flanders as a key hub for innovation and collaboration in collection management and biodiversity science.

Advancing Central African collections and capacity building

Over the next decade, Meise Botanic Garden will focus on strengthening the restoration, digitisation, and sustainable management of botanical collections in Central Africa. Building on decades of collaboration and successful projects with organisations and institutions such as the Center for International Forestry Research (CIFOR), Institut National pour l’Étude et la Recherche Agronomiques (INERA), University of Kisangani, and Institut Congolais pour la Conservation de la Nature (ICCN), we aim to further rehabilitate and digitise herbaria and living collections, particularly in the Democratic Republic of the Congo, while strengthening local capacity and expertise to ensure the long-term preservation and use of these invaluable resources.

Key initiatives include enhancing infrastructure, such as upgrading storage facilities, providing equipment for digitisation, and ensuring sustainable energy supplies, as already achieved at the Yangambi herbarium. The Yangambi herbarium, home to approximately 150,000 specimens, is one of the most significant collections in Central Africa. These collections serve as critical resources for advancing biodiversity research, conservation including IUCN red listing, and sustainable forest management and reforestation projects in the region.

Training and capacity building will be integral to this vision. By equipping local herbarium staff and botanists with the skills needed for collection management, digitisation, and biodiversity informatics, we aim to create a strong foundation for independent and locally-driven research and conservation initiatives. This includes organising workshops on fieldwork, specimen identification, databasing, and digital accessibility, empowering Central African institutions to take a leading role in managing their botanical heritage.

By unlocking historical data and revitalising key collections, such as those in Yangambi and Luki Biosphere Reserve, we aim to transform these sites into hubs for modern research on biodiversity, wood biology, sustainable forestry, and climate change monitoring. Through these efforts, the Garden seeks to position Central Africa’s botanical collections as globally significant resources for science, conservation, and sustainable development. These initiatives should prioritise approaches where Central African partners help define the objectives, while the Garden provides support and expertise to help achieve their goals, enabling equitable and mutually beneficial collaborations.

Meise Botanic Garden plays an active role in the restoration and digitisation of the Democratic Republic of the Congo's unique biodiversity resources through collaborations with local partners, such as the herbarium of the Institut National pour l'Étude et la Recherche Agronomiques at the Yangambi Research Station. Credit: Axel Fassio, CIFOR.

Goals by 2035

- The Garden is a pivotal contributor to the DiSSCo infrastructure, integrating collections across Belgium and Europe, improving digital accessibility, and advancing technologies to enable interdisciplinary research.
- The Garden is recognised worldwide as a leader in collection management and biodiversity informatics, sharing expertise and best practices to promote international collaboration.
- The Garden has expanded strategic partnerships, particularly in Central Africa, to co-develop and digitally reunite collections, enhance infrastructure, and build local expertise, transforming collections like those in Yangambi into modern research hubs for biodiversity, sustainable forestry, and climate change studies.

Acronyms used

BGCI: Botanic Gardens Conservation International.

BiCIKL: Biodiversity Community Integrated Knowledge Library (EU project).

BOLD: Barcode of Life Data Systems.

CARE: Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, Ethics. A set of principles intended to guide open data projects in engaging indigenous peoples rights and interests.

CBD: Convention on Biological Diversity.

CETAF: Consortium of European Taxonomic Facilities.

CITES: Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora.

CMS: Collection Management System.

DES: Digital Extended Specimen.

DiSSCo: Distributed System of Scientific Collections (European research infrastructure).

DOI: Digital Object Identifier.

EOSC: European Open Science Cloud.

FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

FWB: Fédération Wallonie-Bruxelles

FOSB: Flemish Open Science Board.

FOURCAST: Forest cold and Urban heat island effects on Climate Adaptation of biodiversity (BELSPO project).

FRDN: Flemish Research Data Network

GBIF: Global Biodiversity Information Facility.

GGBN: Global Genome Biodiversity Network.

GSPC: Global Strategy for Plant Conservation.

GTI: Global Taxonomy Initiative.

iBOL: International Barcode of Life project.

IUCN: International Union for Conservation of Nature.

JSTOR: Journal STORage; a digital library of academic journals, books, and primary sources.

LIFE: L'Instrument Financier pour l'Environnement; EU's funding instrument for the environment and climate action.

SPNHC: Society for the Preservation of Natural History Collections.

SYNTHESYS: Synthesis of Systematic Resources (series of EU-funded projects).

TDWG: Biodiversity Information Standards.

TETRIS: Transforming European Taxonomy through Training, Research and Innovations (EU project).

Colophon

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Use of Artificial Intelligence

This text was originally written by a human author. ChatGPT was used to assist with grammar, style, and clarity improvements. The final version was reviewed and approved by a human editor to ensure accuracy and coherence.

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